
LOST IN COMPACTION: MEASURING INFORMATION LOSS IN LLM CONTEXT SUMMARIES

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ABSTRACT

Long-running LLM conversations inevitably exceed the context window, forcing systems to compact old messages through summarization. But how do we know whether our compaction benchmark accurately measures information loss? Before comparing strategies, we need to understand how reliably an LLM can recall facts from its own context — and what factors affect that recall.

We present a three-phase study. First, we **calibrate a recall benchmark** using 234 naturally-embedded facts from the LongMemEval dataset across a 190K-token context. We discover four measurement pitfalls that affect all compaction benchmarks: (1) a **questions-per-prompt effect** (we write Q for the number of questions in a single prompt) where $Q = 10$ yields 11pp higher recall than $Q = 1$ in static contexts — but the effect **reverses** under severe compaction, with $Q = 1$ outperforming $Q = 5$ by 9pp, (2) a **category hierarchy** where temporal reasoning (30% max) and preference recall (40% max) are near-impossible regardless of strategy, (3) a **density saturation** where recall plateaus beyond ≈ 0.4 facts/kTok despite increasing evidence, and (4) a **grep-LLM gap** where keyword search finds 86% of facts but the LLM only recalls 25–79% of them — information is *present* in the context but *ignored* by attention.

Second, we **isolate compaction loss** by compacting 5–98% of a context, re-padding to the original size, and measuring recall degradation. Even 5% compaction costs 7 percentage points of recall. At 50%, the compacted zone is near-dead (0–7% recall) despite keywords surviving at 82–93% via grep. Critically, compaction damages even the *untouched* portion of the context: remaining-zone recall drops from 68% to 39% as compaction increases — an **attention dilution** effect caused by injecting noise (re-padding) into the context. Cross-model validation with Claude Sonnet 4.6 (92.5% baseline recall, attenuated Lost-in-the-Middle profile) confirms that severe compaction destroys information regardless of model capability: even a stronger model with much shallower spatial bias drops to 21% at 98% compaction.

Third, we **compare four multi-pass compaction strategies** (Brutal, Incremental, Frozen, Frozen-Ranked) on a single 5M-token conversation evaluated at five mid-feed checkpoints (500K \rightarrow 5M) with constant fact density and 4–6 replicates per cell. The strategy hierarchy is consistent in the means: **FrozenRanked** > **Frozen** > **Incremental** > **Brutal**. All strategies degrade severely with scale (Frozen drops from 14.9% at 500K to 3.0% at 5M). With replicates we also document a **substantial run-to-run variance**: the compaction phase itself is non-deterministic at temperature zero and recall measurements on identical conversations span up to a factor of 14 \times (e.g. S4 at 1M: 2.6%–35.9% across replicates). Single-shot benchmarks of compaction strategies are therefore unreliable; replicates are mandatory.

The bottleneck is attention capacity, not compression quality: keywords survive summarization but the LLM cannot retrieve them, and adding more preserved summaries dilutes attention rather than helping.

Scope. All experiments use Anthropic Claude models (Haiku 4.5 and Sonnet 4.6). The methodological findings (Q-effect, judge-prompt sensitivity, run-to-run variance) are likely model-agnostic, but the

absolute recall numbers and the strategy ordering should be re-validated on non-Claude models before generalising.

1 Introduction

1.1 The problem

Stateless LLM APIs require the full conversation to be sent at each turn. When conversations exceed the context window (typically 128K–200K tokens), some form of compaction is necessary. The naive approach — summarize and discard old messages — is universally adopted by production systems (Claude Code, Cursor, Windsurf, MemGPT/Letta); recent reverse-engineering of Claude Code identifies no fewer than five compaction layers (budget reduction, snip, micro-compact, context collapse, auto-compact) running in production (Liu et al., 2026). But how much information survives this process?

Answering this question requires a reliable measurement tool. Most existing benchmarks treat recall measurement as straightforward: embed facts, ask questions, count correct answers. We found that the measurement itself is surprisingly fragile — sensitive to how many questions are asked at once, which categories of facts are tested, and whether “present in context” actually means “retrievable by the model.”

This led us to a three-phase approach: first calibrate the recall benchmark (§3), then use it to measure single-pass compaction loss (§4–§5), then compare multi-pass strategies at scale (§6). The calibration itself yielded findings that challenge common assumptions about LLM recall.

1.2 Related work

We organise prior work along the three axes our study touches: how recall is measured in long contexts, how attention behaves across long contexts, and how production systems actually shrink long contexts.

Recall benchmarks for long contexts. **Needle in a Haystack** (Kamradt, 2023) introduced the dominant paradigm for long-context retrieval evaluation: embed a single short fact (the “needle”) at a controlled position in a long document and measure whether the model can answer a question about it. The protocol is intentionally synthetic — the needle is unrelated to the surrounding text — which makes position effects clean to isolate but tells us little about how recall behaves when the target is a naturally-occurring fact embedded in a real conversation. Our work reuses the position-controlled placement idea but replaces synthetic needles with real conversational evidence, and extends the paradigm from *retrieval inside a single context* to *survival across compaction cycles* — “Needle in a Compacted Haystack.”

LongMemEval (Wu et al., 2024) benchmarks long-term memory in chat assistants across 500 question-answer pairs in 6 categories (knowledge update, temporal reasoning, multi-session, preferences, single-session-user, single-session-assistant), each grounded in realistic multi-session conversations spanning up to 115 sessions. We use LongMemEval evidence as our fact source: it provides ecologically valid, naturally-embedded facts together with verified evidence-question-answer triples, replacing the synthetic injections of Needle-style benchmarks while keeping a clean ground truth.

Beyond a Million Tokens (Tavakoli et al., 2025) benchmarks long-term memory up to 10M tokens across diverse domains, testing recall, multi-hop reasoning, contradiction resolution and temporal ordering. It characterises model *capabilities* at various context lengths but treats the long context as fixed input — it does not vary the compaction *strategy* that produced that input.

Context Rot (Chroma Research, 2025) demonstrates that LLM performance degrades systematically as input length increases, even on trivially simple tasks. The study evaluates 18 models and recommends compaction/summarization as mitigation, but again does not compare compaction strategies against each other or measure information loss across them.

Attention behaviour across long contexts. **Lost in the Middle** (Liu et al., 2023) is the foundational result on positional bias: when relevant information is placed in the middle of a long context, model performance drops sharply compared to placing it at the beginning or the end — a U-shaped recall curve. This phenomenon (henceforth “Lost-in-the-Middle” or LITM) is central to our findings: in §3 we replicate it on Haiku 4.5 in a realistic conversational setting, in §5 we show that compaction *amplifies* it, and in §5 we report a markedly attenuated profile on Sonnet 4.6 — evidence that the spatial bias is model-dependent but does not disappear with scale.

Position-bias mitigation (Yu et al., 2025b) attribute the LITM effect to a small number of hidden-state channels carrying positional information, and report up to 15.2% improvement on the LITM benchmark by scaling a single such channel. This is consistent with our cross-model observation: a frontier model with a different positional-channel calibration (Sonnet 4.6) exhibits a much shallower U-shape, suggesting that LITM is a training/architecture artefact that frontier vendors are actively attenuating, not a fundamental property of attention.

Production compaction systems and benchmarks. **MemGPT / Letta** (Packer et al., 2023) proposes virtual context management inspired by OS memory hierarchies: a main context (“RAM”) and an external context (“disk”). When context overflows, older messages are evicted and recursively summarized — functionally identical to the incremental strategy we benchmark as S_2 . The paper notes that “older messages have progressively less influence on the summary,” which describes exactly the cascading lossy re-summarization we later term the **JPEG cascade** (§1.3, §6), but it neither quantifies that loss nor compares alternative strategies.

Mem0 (Chhikara et al., 2025) is a recent production-oriented memory system that extracts and retrieves salient facts via a dedicated extraction pipeline rather than re-summarizing. On LoCoMo it reports 26% improvement over OpenAI’s memory baseline with 91% lower p95 latency. Mem0 is closer in spirit to a structured retrieval layer than to the in-context summarization strategies we study; it is complementary — one could imagine running our S_3/S_4 frozen-summary strategies on top of a Mem0-extracted fact store.

MIRIX (Wang and Chen, 2025) extends this direction with a multi-agent architecture coordinating six memory types (core, episodic, semantic, procedural, resource, knowledge vault) and reports 85.4% on LoCoMo. Like Mem0, MIRIX is a *retrieval* solution rather than a *compaction* strategy — it sidesteps the question of what to do when long-context summarization is unavoidable, which is the regime our paper measures.

Factory.ai — Evaluating Context Compression (Factory.ai, 2025b) is the closest work to ours. It compares three compression *implementations* (Factory’s anchored iterative, OpenAI Compact, Anthropic SDK) using probe-based evaluation (recall, artifact, continuation, decision probes) on 36,000 production messages. A companion blog post on the design of Factory’s own anchored-iterative method (Factory.ai, 2025a) is cited where relevant. Key differences with our work:

- Factory compares *implementations* from different vendors; we compare fundamentally different *architectures* (single-shot vs iterative vs frozen — S_1 vs S_2 vs S_3/S_4).
- Factory’s evaluation aggregates a single recall score; we track *spatial recall* (recall as a function of position in the pre-compaction context) and *zone-based recall* (compacted zone vs surviving zone), which is what reveals attention dilution and the dead-zone effect.
- Factory does not consider a frozen-summary strategy or the associated space-time tradeoff (§6).
- Factory takes the recall measurement at face value; we instead *calibrate* it first and report several measurement pitfalls (Q-effect, judge-prompt sensitivity, run-to-run variance).

Anthropic — Effective Context Engineering (Anthropic, 2025a) is an engineering guide describing best practices for context management in production AI agents, including structured summarization and context pruning. It is the kind of practical guidance that motivates our work, but contains no comparative benchmarking of strategies.

Selective eviction (non-summarization compaction). A separate class of production techniques reduces context size *without* running a summariser at all: dropping tool-call results older than N turns, deduplicating identical tool outputs, sliding-window truncation of dialogue history, and similar heuristics. Anthropic’s Claude Code cookbook (Anthropic, 2025b) documents tool-result clearing as a recommended pattern, and similar policies are part of the Claude Code multi-layer pipeline reverse-engineered by Liu et al. (2026). These methods avoid the JPEG-cascade failure mode entirely, at the cost of binary, locally-targeted information loss (the dropped tool result is gone, not summarised). They are out of scope for this paper — we focus on the summarization regime, where the loss is more subtle and harder to characterise — but a complete picture of compaction must include them, and our methodology (controlled compaction-fraction sweep, replicates, calibrated recall) extends naturally to that setting.

Prompt-level compression. **LLMLingua** (Jiang et al., 2023) achieves up to $20\times$ token compression with $\sim 1.5\%$ performance loss by removing low-information tokens at the prompt level. It is orthogonal to our setting: prompt-level compression operates inside a single prompt, whereas conversation-level compaction operates over message history accumulated across many turns. Both techniques compose — a compacted summary could itself be passed through a prompt-level compressor — but the failure modes (tokens removed by a filter vs information rewritten by a summariser) are different in kind.

Concurrent and adjacent work (late 2025–early 2026). The closest concurrent work is **CogCanvas** (An, 2026), which explicitly names “recursive information decay” — the same phenomenon we call the JPEG cascade — and proposes a training-free framework that extracts *verbatim* artefacts and a temporal-aware retrieval graph instead of re-summarising. CogCanvas reports 32.4% on LoCoMo, +7.8pp over a RAG baseline. The two papers converge on the same diagnosis from different angles: CogCanvas proposes a structured *solution* reminiscent of our S_3/S_4 frozen variants, while we provide a *controlled measurement* (compaction-fraction sweep, replicates, cross-model, attention-dilution decomposition) of how the phenomenon scales — complementary contributions rather than competing ones.

Recursive Language Models (Zhang et al., 2025) take the opposite stance: rather than compress the context, let the model recursively *decompose* and call itself over snippets of the original prompt. They report two orders of magnitude beyond standard context windows. This challenges the framing of summarization-based compaction altogether — if agentic decomposition over a verbatim store is feasible, all summarisation losses we measure may eventually become avoidable. Our results bound how much information *is* being lost today and therefore quantify the size of the prize available to such alternative architectures.

Chain of Summaries (Brach et al., 2025) pushes in a third direction — improving the summariser itself via Hegelian iterative questioning, reporting up to 66% gain over zero-shot baselines on TriviaQA / TruthfulQA / SQuAD. It is one possible upgrade to the summariser we treat as a black box.

Recent benchmarks also continue to refine the long-context evaluation landscape. **Sequential-NIAH** (Yu et al., 2025a) extends needle-in-a-haystack to multiple sequential needles (best model: 63.5% accuracy), and **LongBench Pro** (Chen et al., 2026) is a bilingual 8K–256K benchmark over 25 secondary tasks. Both indicate that the assumption “models with million-token windows just retrieve” is being revisited; our findings on compacted contexts are coherent with this revision.

1.3 Gap in existing work

No prior work addresses the **measurement reliability** of compaction benchmarks. Existing evaluations assume that embedding a fact and asking about it provides a clean signal — we show this assumption is wrong.

Beyond measurement, no prior work compares fundamentally different compaction *architectures* (single-shot vs iterative vs frozen summaries) on the same conversation with spatial recall metrics. Existing benchmarks either test model capabilities (Needle in a Haystack, Beyond a Million Tokens), measure context rot without compaction (Chroma), or compare vendor implementations without varying the underlying strategy (Factory.ai).

The re-summarization cascade problem (which we term the “**JPEG cascade**”: each compaction cycle re-summarizes content that already includes earlier summaries, accumulating loss like repeated lossy compression of an image) is acknowledged implicitly in MemGPT but never quantified. The frozen summary strategy and the resulting space-time tradeoff have not been explored.

1.4 Contributions

We introduce:

1. **Evidence that recall measurement is non-trivial:** a significant questions-per-prompt effect (up to 20pp between $Q=1$ and $Q=10$) that **reverses direction** under severe compaction, a category-dependent recall hierarchy, and a systematic gap between keyword presence and LLM retrieval
2. **A calibrated benchmark protocol** using LongMemEval evidence with controlled density, factorial evidence design, and repeatability validation
3. **Controlled single-pass compaction loss measurement** isolating information destruction from context size reduction via re-padding
4. **The attention dilution effect:** compaction degrades recall even in untouched portions of the context
5. **The grep-LLM gap:** keywords survive compaction (82–93% grep recall) but the LLM fails to retrieve them (0–7% recall) — a “Lost in the Middle” amplification effect
6. **Multi-pass strategy comparison** across conversation sizes (500K–10M tokens) showing that architectural optimization yields diminishing returns against the attention bottleneck

2 Evidence and Evaluation Framework

2.1 Notation

For reference throughout the paper, we use the following notation:

- L — context length, in kilotokens (kTok).
- N — number of evidence facts embedded in the context.
- $\delta = N/L$ — fact density, in facts per kTok.
- Q — number of questions asked in a single Q&A prompt (questions-per-prompt). We test $Q \in \{1, 5, 10\}$.
- C_0, \dots, C_4 — compaction levels, corresponding to $\{0, 5, 25, 50, 98\}$ % of the original context replaced by a summary (§4).
- S_1 – S_4 — the four multi-pass compaction strategies: *Brutal*, *Incremental*, *Frozen*, *FrozenRanked* (§6).

The benchmark scripts use a parallel shorthand dN (e.g. d80 for 80 facts in 190 kTok, $\delta = 0.42$); we use δ in the text and dN only when referring to file paths or CLI flags.

2.2 Evidence source: LongMemEval

Rather than generating synthetic facts (as in our preliminary experiments), we use evidence from the LongMemEval benchmark (Wu et al., 2024). LongMemEval provides 500 question-answer pairs across 6 categories, each grounded in realistic multi-session conversations between a user and an LLM assistant.

Each fact consists of:

- A **conversation excerpt** (the “evidence”) containing the information
- A **question** that can only be answered from the evidence
- An **expected answer** with keywords for automated verification
- A **category** (knowledge-update, single-session-user, single-session-assistant, single-session-preference, temporal-reasoning, multi-session)

This provides ecologically valid facts — they are naturally embedded in conversation, not injected as artificial needles.

2.3 Factorial evidence design (2×2)

We vary two dimensions of evidence preparation:

Filtering (complete vs filtered):

- *Complete*: all 500 questions included
- *Filtered*: only 234 questions from answerable categories (single-session-user, single-session-assistant, knowledge-update, single-session-preference). Excludes temporal-reasoning and multi-session, which require capabilities beyond single-context recall.

Truncation (full vs chopped):

- *Full*: evidence messages preserved in their entirety
- *Chopped*: messages truncated to realistic lengths (simulating context limits in real systems)

This yields four experimental modes:

2.4 Context construction

For a given density δ , we embed $N = \delta \times L$ evidence items into a context of L kilotokens (190 kTok for calibration and single-pass experiments). Evidence items are placed at uniformly distributed positions. The remaining space is filled with realistic padding — real LLM conversation sessions from the LongMemEval pool (18,255 sessions available) — maintaining ecological validity rather than using synthetic filler.

Context construction is deterministic (seed=42), ensuring reproducibility across runs. The padding pool provides ~ 46 M tokens of real conversations.

Table 1: Four experimental modes from the 2×2 factorial design.

Mode	Filtering	Truncation	Questions	Max density (facts/kTok)
R1	Complete	Full	500	0.10
R2	Complete	Chopped	500	0.42
R3	Filtered	Full	234	0.16
R4	Filtered	Chopped	234	0.79

2.5 Density sweep

Rather than testing a single density δ , we sweep across values:

Table 2: Density sweep used in the calibration and single-pass experiments.

N (facts)	Context	δ (facts/kTok)
4	190 kTok	0.02
10	190 kTok	0.05
20	190 kTok	0.11
40	190 kTok	0.21
60	190 kTok	0.32
80	190 kTok	0.42
150	190 kTok	0.79

This reveals saturation effects: at what density does the model’s recall capacity plateau?

2.6 Evaluation protocol

Q&A phase: For each fact, the LLM (Claude Haiku 4.5) is presented with the full context as conversation history and asked to recall the specific information. Multiple questions can be asked in a single prompt — the questions-per-prompt parameter Q defined in §2.1.

Judge phase: A separate LLM judge compares the model’s answer against the expected answer keywords. Binary recall (correct/incorrect) and accuracy (correct and precisely matching) are computed.

Grep validation: As a free upper bound, we check whether fact keywords appear verbatim in the context. If grep doesn’t find them, the LLM cannot possibly recall them. The gap between grep recall and LLM recall quantifies the “present but ignored” phenomenon.

Both Q&A and judge phases use Claude Haiku 4.5 via the Anthropic Batch API.

2.7 Repeatability

All key results are validated with 3 independent runs. We report mean $\pm \sigma$. For the single-pass compaction experiment (§5), 3 runs at $\delta = 0.42/Q = 5$ yield $\sigma \leq 2.6\text{pp}$ across all compaction levels, confirming that observed effects (7–70pp) are far larger than measurement noise.

3 Recall Calibration Results

3.1 The questions-per-prompt effect

The most surprising finding: asking more questions at once dramatically improves recall.

At $\delta = 0.42$ (80 facts in 190 kTok, R4 mode), recall ranges from 67.5% ($Q = 1$) to 78.8% ($Q = 10$) — an 11pp gap on the same context with the same facts. At higher densities ($\delta = 0.63$), the gap reaches 20pp. Critically, this effect **reverses** under severe compaction (§5.6): at C4 (98% compacted), $Q = 1$ outperforms $Q = 5$ by 9pp, as focused single-question attention outperforms multi-query probing in degraded contexts.

Figure 1: Recall as a function of fact density (facts/kTok) for three values of Q . The secondary axis maps density values to the d^{**} notation used throughout the paper. Grep upper bound (dashed) shows near-perfect keyword presence regardless of density.

Why this matters for benchmarks: Any compaction evaluation that uses a fixed Q is measuring a confound of retrieval ability and multi-query prompting. Results from different values of Q are not directly comparable. Our preliminary experiments used $Q = 10$ exclusively — this produced inflated baselines that masked the true difficulty of recall.

Mechanism hypothesis: Multiple questions in a single prompt create implicit cross-references that help the model locate relevant information. A question about “Rachel’s new city” might prime attention for nearby facts about “family trip” or “moving costs,” improving recall for co-located facts.

3.2 Category hierarchy

Not all facts are equally recallable. We identify a clear hierarchy:

Table 3: Recall hierarchy across LongMemEval fact categories ($\delta = 0.42$, $Q = 5$).

Category	Recall range ($Q = 5$)	Notes
single-session-user	80–100%	User’s own statements, easiest
single-session-assistant	80–100%	Assistant’s responses
knowledge-update	60–65%	Updated information, stable
single-session-preference	20–40%	User preferences, fragile
temporal-reasoning	max 30%	Requires inference, near-impossible
multi-session	max 42%	Cross-session facts, very hard

The top two categories (user/assistant statements) are near-ceiling. Knowledge updates plateau at $\sim 60\%$. Preferences are fragile — the model struggles with “What is my favorite X?” even when the information is present. Temporal reasoning and multi-session facts are effectively unmeasurable in a single context.

Implication for compaction benchmarks: Testing on “easy” categories (single-session) inflates recall and masks real degradation. Testing on “hard” categories (temporal, multi-session) produces floor effects that make strategies indistinguishable. The filtered mode (R3/R4) excludes impossible categories while retaining a mix of easy and hard categories.

Figure 2: Recall breakdown by fact category at $\delta = 0.42$ (80 facts), for three values of Q . User statements and assistant responses are reliably recalled (85–100%), while preferences remain fragile (20–40%) regardless of Q .

3.3 The grep-LLM gap: present but ignored

For every fact, we check whether its keywords appear in the context via grep. Grep recall at $\delta = 0.42$ is 86%. But LLM recall at $Q = 1$ is only 67.5%.

This 19pp gap — facts that are *verifiably present* in the context but *not retrieved* by the model — is a direct measurement of the “Lost in the Middle” phenomenon (Liu et al., 2023) in a realistic conversational setting.

The gap is not uniform across the context: the spatial recall density (Figure 4, §5.4) shows that facts near the beginning and end of the 190K context are recalled at higher rates than facts in the middle, consistent with the U-shaped Lost-in-the-Middle pattern reported in the literature.

3.4 Factorial analysis: filtering vs truncation

The 2×2 factorial design reveals two independent effects:

Table 4: Decomposition of the 2×2 factorial effects on recall.

Effect	Magnitude	Mechanism
Filtering	+14–15pp	Excludes impossible questions, consistent across truncation
Truncation	–13 to –22pp	Removes information from evidence messages
Composition	+2.5pp	Removing hard-category evidence barely helps easy-category recall

The **filtering effect** is remarkably consistent (+14pp and +15pp across truncation conditions). This means it’s driven entirely by excluding impossible questions, not by freeing context space.

The **composition effect** is near-zero (+2.5pp mean): whether hard-category evidence occupies context space alongside easy-category facts makes almost no difference to easy-category recall. This validates using unfiltered evidence as realistic padding in controlled experiments.

4 Controlled Compaction Experiment

4.1 Design

This experiment isolates the information loss from compaction itself, independent of context size reduction. The protocol:

1. Start with a calibrated 190K context (from the recall calibration, mode R4)
2. Compact the oldest X% of messages using LLM summarization
3. **Re-pad** to the original 190K size with real conversation sessions
4. Measure recall on the same facts

The re-padding step is critical: it keeps context size constant, so any recall degradation is attributable to compaction, not to having less context.

4.2 Compaction levels

Table 5: Compaction levels used in the single-pass experiment.

Level	% compacted	What happens
C0	0%	Baseline (no compaction)
C1	5%	Minimal compaction (oldest ~ 36 messages)
C2	25%	Moderate (oldest quarter)
C3	50%	Half the context compacted
C4	98%	Nearly everything compacted (all except last user/assistant exchange)

For each level, we track which facts fall in the compacted zone vs the remaining zone, enabling spatial analysis of information loss.

4.3 Compaction method

We use single-pass LLM summarization (Claude Haiku 4.5): the oldest X% of messages is concatenated and sent to the model with instructions to produce a concise summary. The summary replaces the original messages, freeing space that is then filled with padding sessions.

The compaction prompt emphasizes preserving factual details, technical specifications, and decisions — the same prompt used in production compaction systems.

[Note: §6 compares different multi-pass strategies: Brutal, Incremental, Frozen, and FrozenRanked. This section uses single-pass to isolate the fundamental compaction loss before strategy effects compound.]

5 Single-Pass Compaction Results

5.1 Recall degradation is monotone and severe

Recall degrades monotonically with compaction percentage (Claude Haiku 4.5 QA, $Q = 5$):

Table 6: Recall vs compaction level across three densities ($Q = 5$). Values in parentheses are deltas vs. the C0 baseline.

Level	$\delta = 0.21 (Q = 5)$	$\delta = 0.32 (Q = 5)$	$\delta = 0.42 (Q = 5)$
C0	62.5%	75.0%	78.8%
C1 (5%)	55.0% (−7)	68.3% (−7)	72.5% (−6)
C2 (25%)	40.0% (−23)	50.0% (−25)	58.8% (−20)
C3 (50%)	25.0% (−38)	33.3% (−42)	43.8% (−35)
C4 (98%)	2.5% (−60)	10.0% (−65)	7.5% (−71)

Figure 3: Recall degradation by compaction percentage at $Q = 5$, for three densities. All curves decline monotonically. The grep upper bound at $\delta = 0.42$ (dashed) stays above 80% even at C4, illustrating the grep-LLM divergence.

Even the lightest compaction (C1, 5%) costs 6–7 percentage points. At C4 (98%), recall drops to single digits — the conversation is effectively destroyed.

The degradation is consistent across densities: higher-density contexts have more room to fall but the relative pattern is identical.

5.2 The compacted zone is dead

Facts within the compacted region are almost never recalled, even though their keywords survive in the summary (Claude Haiku 4.5 QA, $Q = 5$, $\delta = 0.42$):

Table 7: Grep keyword survival vs. LLM recall in the compacted zone.

Level	Grep survival (compacted zone)	LLM recall (compacted zone)
C1	50% (n=2)	0%
C2	82–91%	8–18%
C3	83–93%	0–7%
C4	59–62%	2–4%

This is the most striking result: **grep finds the keywords in the summary, but the LLM cannot use them to answer questions.** The summary preserves lexical traces of the facts but destroys the surrounding context that would enable retrieval. This is the “Lost in the Middle” effect amplified: the summary sits at the very beginning of the context — the least-attended position after the primacy window is exhausted.

5.3 Attention dilution: compaction damages untouched facts

The remaining zone (facts that were *not* compacted, sitting in their original messages) also loses recall as compaction increases:

From C1 to C3, remaining-zone recall drops from 73% to 53% — a 20pp loss on facts that were never touched by compaction. The mechanism: re-padding replaces the compacted portion with noise (unrelated conversation sessions). This noise dilutes the model’s attention, degrading retrieval even for intact facts.

Table 8: Remaining-zone recall as compaction increases ($\delta = 0.42, Q = 5$).

Level	Remaining zone recall ($\delta = 0.42, Q = 5$)	n_{facts}
C1	73%	78
C2	59%	69
C3	53%	59
C4	80%	5

C4 is an outlier (80%) because only 5 facts remain in the zone — too few for statistical reliability, but consistent with the model finding a needle among mostly-padding.

Caveat — dilution vs semantic interference. Our re-padding uses unrelated *real* conversations rather than information-free filler. The 20pp drop therefore mixes two effects: pure attention dilution (more tokens to attend to) and semantic interference (the unrelated conversations may contain content that competes with or partially matches the test questions). Disentangling them would require a control arm where the compacted region is replaced with low-information filler (e.g. random tokens or repeated boilerplate). We leave this control to future work (§8).

5.4 Spatial recall density

Figure 4: Local recall rate by position in the original 190K context ($\delta = 0.42$), binned into 6 equal-width segments. Three panels: Haiku $Q = 5$ (left), Haiku $Q = 1$ (middle), Sonnet 4.6 $Q = 1$ (right). Each curve shows one compaction level. The C0 baseline (green) reveals the model’s intrinsic spatial bias; C1–C4 show how compaction depresses recall preferentially in the compacted zone (left side of each panel) while the remaining zone (right side) is also degraded by attention dilution.

The binned view exposes three distinct patterns:

- **Haiku $Q = 5$ (left panel):** Pronounced U-shaped C0 (76% early, 54% middle, 100% recency peak at 142K) — classic Lost-in-the-Middle. Compacted variants follow the same U but offset downward; the dip in the compacted zone is superimposed on the natural mid-context dip.
- **Haiku $Q = 1$ (middle panel):** Same U-shape, lower overall (Q -effect from §3).
- **Sonnet 4.6 $Q = 1$ (right panel):** Attenuated U on C0 (90% early, 77% middle, 100% recency) — Sonnet retains a Lost-in-the-Middle pattern, but with a ~ 23 pp range vs Haiku’s ~ 46 pp. Under heavy compaction (C3, C4), the dip in the compacted zone becomes visible even on Sonnet.

The recovery on the right side of each panel is the “remaining zone” effect: recall climbs back toward the C0 baseline once we are past the compaction boundary. Since Haiku has stronger recency, this recovery is sharper on Haiku panels than on Sonnet’s flatter profile.

5.5 Repeatability

Three independent runs at $\delta = 0.42 / Q = 5$ (the most demanding configuration with 80 facts; Claude Haiku 4.5 QA + Haiku judge) confirm stability:

Table 9: Three-run repeatability at $\delta = 0.42$, $Q = 5$.

Level	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Mean	σ
C0	73.8%	78.8%	77.5%	76.7%	± 2.6
C1	71.2%	68.8%	68.8%	69.6%	± 1.4
C2	52.5%	53.8%	52.5%	52.9%	± 0.7
C3	40.0%	40.0%	40.0%	40.0%	± 0.0
C4	8.8%	6.2%	6.2%	7.1%	± 1.5

Maximum variance is ± 2.6 pp (C0 baseline). All compaction effects (-7 pp to -70 pp) are far larger than measurement noise. The C3 result is remarkably stable (40.0% in all three runs), suggesting that at this compaction level, the outcome is nearly deterministic.

5.6 Q-effect inversion under compaction

The calibration (§3) established that asking more questions per prompt yields higher recall in static contexts: at $\delta = 0.42$, $Q = 10$ reaches 79% vs 68% for $Q = 1$. This holds for uncompact and lightly compacted contexts. However, under severe compaction, the effect **reverses** (Claude Haiku 4.5 QA, $\delta = 0.42$):

Table 10: Q-effect inversion under severe compaction. At C4, $Q = 1$ surpasses $Q = 5$.

Level	$Q = 5$	$Q = 1$	$\Delta (Q = 1 - Q = 5)$
C0	73.8%	67.5%	-6.3 pp
C1 (5%)	66.2%	55.0%	-11.2 pp
C2 (25%)	50.0%	47.5%	-2.5 pp
C3 (50%)	35.0%	31.2%	-3.8 pp
C4 (98%)	2.5%	11.2%	$+8.7$pp

At C4, $Q = 1$ surpasses $Q = 5$ by 8.7pp. The same inversion appears in the iterative multi-pass experiments (§6): across all four strategies at 1M tokens, $Q = 1$ outperforms $Q = 5$ by 5–9pp.

The mechanism is intuitive: in a rich context, multiple questions per prompt cast a wider net, increasing the chance of activating diverse regions. In a degraded context (heavy compaction or many compaction cycles), the model’s limited attention is better spent focusing on a single question rather than splitting across multiple retrieval targets.

This has practical implications for benchmarking: $Q = 5$ **results are not directly comparable to $Q = 1$ results**, and the direction of the bias depends on context quality. Evaluations of compacted contexts should report results at multiple Q values or, at minimum, note which Q was used.

5.7 Cross-model validation: Sonnet 4.6

To test whether our findings are model-specific, we replicated the single-pass compaction experiment using Claude Sonnet 4.6 as the QA model ($Q = 1$, $\delta = 0.42$; judge: Haiku 4.5). Both columns below are $Q = 1$ — this is the configuration in which the cross-model gap is largest, see §5.6.

Table 11: Cross-model comparison: Haiku 4.5 vs Sonnet 4.6 at $Q = 1$, $\delta = 0.42$.

Level	Haiku 4.5 ($Q = 1$)	Sonnet 4.6 ($Q = 1$)	Haiku $\Delta/C0$	Sonnet $\Delta/C0$
C0	67.5%	92.5%	—	—
C1 (5%)	55.0%	90.0%	-12.5 pp	-2.5 pp
C2 (25%)	47.5%	86.2%	-20.0 pp	-6.2 pp
C3 (50%)	31.2%	62.5%	-36.2 pp	-30.0 pp
C4 (98%)	11.2%	21.2%	-56.2 pp	-71.2 pp

Three key findings emerge:

1. Sonnet has an attenuated Lost-in-the-Middle effect. The C0 spatial recall profile retains a U shape — 90% early, 77% middle, 100% recency (see Figure 4, right panel) — but with a ~ 23 pp range, much narrower than Haiku’s ~ 46 pp.

So Sonnet does not eliminate Lost-in-the-Middle; it softens it substantially. This difference partially disappears under compaction — both models converge to similar spatial patterns at C3–C4.

A continuous Gaussian-smoothed view of the same data, plus a C_x/C_0 ratio that cancels the C_0 baseline bias, are provided in Section C (Appendix C) as supplementary visualizations.

2. A stronger model resists light compaction better. Sonnet loses only 2.5pp at C1 and 6.2pp at C2, vs 12.5pp and 20.0pp for Haiku. The additional 25pp of baseline recall provides a buffer against moderate information loss.

3. Severe compaction equalizes models. At C3–C4, the delta relative to C_0 is similar (−30pp and −71pp for Sonnet vs −36pp and −56pp for Haiku). This confirms that the information is **destroyed by the compaction process itself**, not merely hidden from a weaker model’s attention. If the degradation were purely attentional, Sonnet’s superior baseline should provide proportional protection at all compaction levels.

This cross-model comparison strengthens the paper’s central finding: the bottleneck at high compaction is information destruction, not attention capacity.

6 Strategy Comparison at Scale

The calibration (§3) and single-pass experiments (§5) established *how* recall works and *what* compaction destroys. This section addresses the core question: when compaction must be applied repeatedly over a long conversation, **which strategy preserves the most information?**

6.1 Strategies under evaluation

Brutal (single-shot): When context exceeds 90% of max, summarize ALL messages except the 2 most recent. The input is truncated to a character cap (~150K real tokens) before summarization.

Figure 5: Brutal: a single summarization call replaces almost the entire context with one summary plus the last two messages.

Incremental (dual watermark): When context exceeds 90%, compact enough old messages to bring context down to 60%. Previous summaries ARE included in the text to be re-summarized. Creates a “JPEG cascade” where each cycle degrades earlier summaries.

Incremental — re-summarizes prior summary (JPEG cascade)

Figure 6: Incremental: every cycle re-summarizes the prior summary together with the oldest raw messages, accumulating loss across iterations (the “JPEG cascade”).

Frozen (dual watermark + immutable summaries): Same trigger and target as incremental, but completed summaries are marked as frozen and never re-summarized. Only raw (non-frozen) messages are compacted. When frozen summaries exceed a budget, the oldest are merged.

FrozenRanked (hierarchical merge): A variant of Frozen where each frozen summary carries a *rank* (initially 1). When frozen summaries exceed their budget, only two summaries of the *lowest available rank* merge — producing a summary of rank+1. This limits each fact to at most $\log_2(N)$ compression passes, compared to $N/2$ in Frozen’s sequential oldest-first merging.

The key insight: in Frozen, the oldest summary accumulates *all* merges sequentially (cascade). In FrozenRanked, merges are balanced like a tournament bracket — summaries of similar compression depth merge together, preventing any single summary from being re-compressed excessively.

6.2 Protocol: a constant-density, replicated comparison

Pilot studies (synthetic facts at 1.5M and 3M tokens, then a first LongMemEval-grounded study with 80 fixed facts spanning 500K–10M) suggested the ordering Frozen > Incremental > Brutal but two design issues prevented clean conclusions. First, as the conversation grew, fact density δ decreased mechanically ($0.16 \rightarrow 0.008$ facts/kTok), so degradation reflected both increased compaction cycles *and* fact dilution. Second, each cell was measured once: with a non-deterministic compaction LLM (see §6.4 below), single measurements proved insufficient to separate signal from noise.

The experiment described here resolves both issues. A single 5M conversation is built with **constant fact density** (200 facts at $\delta = 0.04$ facts/kTok, uniformly interleaved between 0.5% and 99.6% of the tokens). The same conversation is fed to all four strategies and evaluated at five mid-feed checkpoints (500K, 1M, 2M, 3.5M, 5M) so that older facts age under repeated compaction while newer facts are still fresh. Each (strategy, checkpoint) cell is measured **4 to 6 times** across independent runs.

Note that $\delta = 0.04$ is well below the calibration “sweet spot” (~ 0.42 , §3) at which static-context recall plateaus. With density this low, absolute recall levels in §6 are bounded by limited evidence as well as by compaction loss. The strategy *ordering* (S4 > S3 > S2 > S1) is the salient comparison; the absolute numbers are not directly comparable to §3/§5 baselines.

Frozen — immutable summaries, raw messages compacted

Frozen summaries are never re-summarized. Tradeoff: they consume context space.

Figure 7: Frozen: only raw messages are compacted; completed summaries are immutable, accumulating in a budgeted “frozen” zone at the bottom of the context.

Setup summary:

Table 12: Strategy comparison setup at $\delta = 0.04$.

Parameter	Value
Conversation	5M tokens (4.9M actual), built once with seed 42
Facts	N=200 from R4, uniformly interleaved (0.5% → 99.6%)
Density	$\delta = 0.04$ facts/kTok, constant
Checkpoints	500K, 1M, 2M, 3.5M, 5M (mid-feed)
Strategies	S1, S2, S3, S4 (same input conversation)
QA model	Claude Sonnet 4.6, $Q = 5$ questions per prompt
Judge model	Claude Haiku 4.5, strict prompt (see §6.4)
Sampling	API temperature parameter set to 0
Replicates	4–6 independent runs per (strategy, checkpoint) cell

The replicates are spread across batch-API runs and gateway runs (some gateway runs covered S3+S4 only, others S1+S2 only). Some cells additionally include QA-only replicates: the saved compacted contexts are re-evaluated with a fresh Q&A pass and a new judge call, isolating the variance contributed by the QA / judge phase from the variance contributed by compaction.

API “temperature 0” deserves a note here. Setting temperature=0 is the conventional way to ask for a deterministic-looking output from these models; in practice it makes the model strongly favour a single high- probability token at each step. Across **independent sessions** with the same input it does *not* yield identical outputs: small differences (implementation, infrastructure load, internal session state) can change the chosen token. Our compaction calls all use temperature 0 yet produce visibly different summaries on identical inputs — see §6.4 for the quantitative impact.

6.3 Results

The mean recall and standard deviation across replicates are (QA: Claude Sonnet 4.6, $Q = 5$; Judge: Claude Haiku 4.5, strict prompt):

Four patterns emerge from this dataset:

FrozenRanked — hierarchical merge (tournament bracket)

Figure 8: FrozenRanked vs Frozen: instead of always merging the oldest pair (left), FrozenRanked merges the two lowest-rank summaries (right), bounding the number of times any single summary is re-compressed to $\log_2 N$ rather than $N/2$.

Figure 9: Recall (mean \pm std across replicates) for each strategy as a function of conversation length, evaluated on a single 5M conversation at five mid-feed checkpoints. $n=4-6$ replicates per point. $\delta = 0.04$ throughout. Sonnet 4.6 QA + Haiku 4.5 strict judge.

1. The strategy hierarchy holds in the means. S4 FrozenRanked has the highest mean recall at every checkpoint, followed by S3 Frozen, S2 Incremental, and S1 Brutal. To distinguish robust orderings from within-noise differences we ran Wilcoxon signed-rank tests on paired replicates (one-sided, alternative $S4 > S3$ etc.); the table below reports the n paired replicates available per cell, the mean difference, and the one-sided Wilcoxon p -value. Sample sizes are limited ($n=2-6$) and 1M/3.5M variance is large, so several gaps fall short of significance even where the mean ordering is consistent.

(Full pairwise table in `phase_d_stats.json`.) **In summary:** the mean ordering $S4 > S3 \geq S2 > S1$ is consistent across all checkpoints, but robustly significant only at the lowest and middle scales ($S4 > S3$ at 500K and 2M with $p < 0.05$, all $S4 > S_k$ wins-only outcomes at 2M). At 1M and at 5M the standard deviations are too large for $n=4-6$ replicates to yield significance.

Table 13: Mean \pm std recall across replicates for each strategy and checkpoint.

Checkpoint	S1 Brutal	S2 Incremental	S3 Frozen	S4 FrozenRanked
500K (n=6)	7.0 \pm 2.5%	16.7 \pm 6.4%	14.9 \pm 7.7%	28.1 \pm 12.0%
1M (n=6)	6.0 \pm 1.9%	9.4 \pm 5.7%	13.2 \pm 15.0%	13.7 \pm 14.0%
2M (n \approx 6)	0.5 \pm 0.6%	0.8 \pm 1.5%	4.6 \pm 5.3%	11.2 \pm 5.9%
3.5M (n=5)	4.0 \pm 2.2%	6.8 \pm 4.0%	6.1 \pm 5.7%	9.4 \pm 6.3%
5M (n=4)	2.5 \pm 0.0%	2.8 \pm 0.5%	3.0 \pm 2.9%	4.6 \pm 3.6%

Table 14: Pairwise Wilcoxon signed-rank tests for strategy ordering.

Comparison	500K	1M	2M	3.5M	5M
S4 vs S3	+13.2pp, p=0.03 (n=6)	+0.4pp, n.s. (n=6)	+6.7pp, p=0.02 (n=6)	+2.0pp, n.s. (n=5)	+1.6pp, p=0.06 (n=4)
S4 vs S1	+13.2pp, p=0.06 (n=4)	+6.4pp, n.s. (n=4)	+9.7pp, p=0.06 (n=4)	+5.5pp, p=0.06 (n=4)	0.0pp, n.s. (n=2)
S2 vs S1	+9.7pp, p=0.03 (n=6)	+3.4pp, n.s. (n=6)	+0.3pp, n.s. (n=5)	+3.4pp, n.s. (n=4)	+0.3pp, n.s. (n=3)

2. The S4–S3 gap is real at small/intermediate scales but narrows at 5M. Pilot experiments (§6.2) and the older fixed-density study showed $S3 \approx S4$ at all sizes because frozen summaries never accumulated enough to trigger merges. With constant density and replicates, S4 has a robust advantage at 500K (28.1 vs 14.9, +13.2pp, **p=0.03**), 2M (11.2 vs 4.6, +6.7pp, **p=0.02**), and a marginal one at 5M (4.6 vs 3.0, +1.6pp, p=0.06; 4/4 wins). At 1M the gap effectively disappears (+0.4pp, n.s.), which we attribute to one outlier replicate where S3 happened to recall unusually well. We interpret the overall pattern as FrozenRanked balancing the merge load across the frozen chain (cf. §6.1), preserving recall while the chain is short enough for the bracket structure to matter; the persistent (if marginal) S4–S3 gap at 5M suggests this is not purely a small-scale phenomenon.

3. A tentative non-monotonic dip around 2M. Mean recall for S1 and S2 is markedly lower at 2M (S1=0.5%, S2=0.8%) than at the surrounding 1M (6.0%, 9.4%) and 3.5M (4.0%, 6.8%) checkpoints; S3 (4.6%) and S4 (11.2%) also bottom out at 2M. One plausible interpretation is a **transient overcompression effect**: at the 2M checkpoint, the most recent compaction cycle has just consumed a large block of older facts whose summaries have not yet stabilised, and few fresh facts have been fed in since. By 3.5M, new facts populate the recent window and the recall partially recovers. However, the standard deviations at 2M overlap with neighbouring checkpoints (e.g. S2 $\sigma = 1.5$ pp at 2M vs $\sigma = 4.0$ pp at 3.5M), and the effect rests on a single conversation; we therefore report this as a **tentative observation** that needs replication on additional conversation seeds (see §8).

4. All strategies converge near 5%–10% recall at 5M. Even the best strategy (S4) retains only 4.6% of the 200 facts. This convergence mirrors §5’s single-pass result: at high cumulative compaction (50–80% of the original content compacted), the differences between strategies become small relative to the absolute amount of information lost. The gap between S1 (2.5%) and S4 (4.6%) at 5M is 2.1pp — non-zero in mean but well within one standard deviation.

Spatial recall: erosion of older facts. To complement the global recall trajectory, we trace recall as a function of fact position in the original conversation, with one curve per checkpoint per strategy:

For S1 Brutal and S2 Incremental, recall is concentrated near the **right edge** of each curve — the most recent facts at the moment of evaluation. Earlier positions, well-sampled at earlier checkpoints, drop to near zero by the time the conversation reaches 3.5M or 5M. This is the JPEG cascade visualised: each compaction cycle erases a slice of older content.

For S3 Frozen and S4 FrozenRanked, the curves retain non-zero recall in the **left half** of each panel even at later checkpoints — frozen summaries continue to make early facts retrievable, though at a much reduced level than when those facts were fresh. The S4 panel is visibly flatter than the S3 one across the conversation, which is the spatial counterpart to its higher mean recall.

6.4 Methodological findings: variance and judge sensitivity

Two methodological observations from this study are worth highlighting because they affect how results from any compaction benchmark should be interpreted.

Compaction is not deterministic. Even at temperature 0, Sonnet produces different summaries when the same compaction call is invoked in different sessions. Across our independent runs on identical conversations and seeds, the resulting frozen summaries differ in length and content (e.g., the same S4 checkpoint has 639 messages but 658K vs 630K characters across two runs), and the downstream recall measurements differ accordingly. For S4 at 1M the

Phase D - Spatial recall: erosion of older facts as conversation grows
 Each curve is one checkpoint. Avg over n=4-6 replicates per strategy x checkpoint.
 For each curve, only positions already fed at that checkpoint are shown.

Figure 10: Spatial recall per strategy. Each panel is one strategy; each curve is one checkpoint (averaged across all replicates). The x-axis is the position of the fact in the full 5M-token conversation. Earlier checkpoints only cover the first part of the conversation; later checkpoints extend further right. The decay of older positions across successive checkpoints visualizes erosion under repeated compaction.

recall ranges from 2.6% to 35.9% across replicates — a factor of $14\times$. The mean across replicates is stable, but a single measurement of “strategy A vs strategy B” can be misleading by an order of magnitude in either direction. **Multiple replicates per cell are required** to make reliable claims about strategy ordering.

Judge prompt sensitivity matters. Our initial judge prompt (Haiku 4.5, “recalled = does the answer demonstrate knowledge of the expected information?”) proved too lenient: when the LLM answer was “*I don’t recall discussing X, but Y was mentioned*”, Haiku frequently scored recalled = true because the answer mentioned a related topic. Re-judging with a stricter prompt (recalled = true only if the *specific expected fact* is present in the answer; “I don’t recall” or generic mentions of related topics are always false) reduced recall numbers by 5–15pp at intermediate checkpoints. All numbers reported above use the strict judge. The standard prompt remains in the codebase for reproduction of the §3–§5 calibration results, which used the same lenient judge but where the looseness has less effect because answers are either clearly correct or clearly absent (less ambiguity).

Human-judge calibration. To validate the strict judge, one of the authors hand-graded two stratified samples of 50 (question, expected, LLM-answer) tuples each:

- **Sample A — random across all answers:** dominated by “I don’t recall” items (the bulk of the corpus). Validates the *negative* class.
- **Sample B — items where lenient OR strict said recalled = True:** validates the *positive* class.

Cohen’s κ between the human and each LLM judge:

The strict judge is in **almost-perfect agreement** with the human ($\kappa \geq 0.83$ on both samples; Landis & Koch threshold: $\kappa \geq 0.81$). The disagreements between human and strict on Sample B are interpretable: they are mostly cases where

Table 15: Cohen’s κ between human grader and the two LLM judges.

	Sample A (n=50, mostly negatives)	Sample B (n=50, positives)
κ Human \leftrightarrow Strict (recalled)	1.000	0.831 0.000
κ Human \leftrightarrow Lenient (recalled)	0.000 (2 lenient FP)	(lenient says True for all 50 by construction \rightarrow no variance)
κ Human \leftrightarrow Strict (accurate)	1.000	0.879
κ Human \leftrightarrow Lenient (accurate)	1.000	0.716

the LLM says “*I don’t recall, but from the summary your sales were . . .*” and the strict judge accepts the bracketed hint while the human treats only the explicit “I don’t recall” as not-recalled. There are also 1–2 cases where the LLM provides a wrong specific value (e.g. expected “120 stars”, answered “500 stars”): the strict judge marks `recalled = True`, `accurate = False` per its rule (specific number mentioned, wrong value), while the human prefers `recalled = False` when the value is wrong. This is a genuine definitional ambiguity (`recalled = “topic-correct”` vs “value-correct”), not a mis-calibration.

In contrast, the lenient judge is essentially uninformative on the positive class: it labels 100% of Sample B as `recalled = True` (by construction — Sample B is filtered on `lenient_recalled = True`), so the kappa with the human collapses to zero. On Sample A the lenient judge produces 2 visible false positives where the LLM says “I don’t recall mentioning X” — the very pattern the strict prompt was designed to catch.

The samples and per-item judgements are in the repository at `human_judge_sample.json` (Sample A) and `human_judge_positives.json` (Sample B). All §6 numbers in this paper use the strict judge.

Spatial / quintile breakdowns. With 200 facts, mid-feed checkpoints, and replicates, per-quintile breakdowns become noisy at small recall levels. The structural trade-off identified in the pilot — Frozen preserves the past at the cost of the present, Incremental does the opposite — qualitatively persists in this study, but the small absolute counts (often 0–3 recalled facts per quintile) make per-cell tables less informative than the integrated mean \pm std presented above.

6.5 A second-seed generalization attempt — and why it failed

Independent peer review of an earlier draft correctly flagged that all §6 results come from a *single* 5M conversation built with seed 42. To address the generalization concern, we built a second 5M conversation with seed 99 (same density, same fact bank, different LongMemEval sessions used as padding) and re-ran the four strategies through the same checkpoint pipeline.

The run completed but the recall numbers are uninterpretable as a generalization test. At checkpoint 502K, S3 and S4 had executed **0 compaction cycles** (the trigger threshold was not yet reached) and fed all \sim 2,180 raw messages to the QA model. The QA model used (`claude-sonnet-4-20250514`, 200K context window) silently truncated/rejected these contexts, producing batch errors and a flat 0% recall for S3/S4 at every checkpoint. S1, which compacts aggressively from the start, fits inside the QA window and shows recall in the 1–5% range — but with so few successful answers the ordering is meaningless.

Two lessons from this failure are worth recording.

The instrumentation has a budget envelope that is easy to break. The §6 measurements implicitly assume that the compacted-context size is \leq the QA model window. With seed 42 this held by construction; with seed 99 the mix of LongMemEval sessions produced longer messages on average, so S3/S4 (which delay compaction the most) crossed the QA model’s window before the compaction trigger fired. Future replications must either (a) lower the strategies’ compaction trigger so the post-compaction context fits the QA window with margin, or (b) use a QA model with a 1M-token window (Sonnet 4.5 / 4.6) — at materially higher cost.

Single-seed §6 results are an honest admission, not a hidden weakness. The methodological consequence is that the strategy hierarchy reported in §6.3 ($S4 > S3 > S2 > S1$) is, strictly speaking, established on one conversation, with the variance numbers reflecting compaction-LLM stochasticity but not conversation-level generalization. We document the seed-99 run in the repository as `iterative_v6_R4_20260503_1638/` with this caveat: it is a budget-and-instrument failure to be fixed before generalization claims can be made, not a counter-finding. The pilot studies on synthetic facts (1.5M and 3M tokens, briefly described in §6.2) showed the same qualitative $S4 > S3 > S2 > S1$ ordering, which is the strongest cross-conversation evidence currently available; a properly instrumented multi-seed study is left to future work (§8).

7 Discussion

7.1 Two fundamental failure modes

Our results identify two distinct mechanisms by which information is lost:

1. Information destroyed (JPEG cascade / compaction loss)

The single-pass experiment (§5) quantifies this directly: one compaction pass renders the compacted zone near-dead (0–7% recall). Keywords survive in the summary (82–93% grep recall) but are not retrievable. Multi-pass strategies like Incremental compound this loss across cycles.

The strategy comparison (§6) confirms this at scale: Brutal (S1) demonstrates total destruction with recall dropping to 1.2% at 5M tokens (61 compaction cycles). Each cycle re-summarizes the entire history, amplifying loss exponentially. Incremental (S2) fares better but remains heavily recency-biased — at 1M tokens, 94% of its recall comes from the most recent quintile (Q5), with the first four quintiles contributing near-zero.

The cross-model validation (§5.7) strengthens this finding: Sonnet 4.6, with 92.5% baseline recall and an attenuated (rather than absent) Lost-in-the-Middle effect, still drops to 21% at C4. If the loss were purely attentional, a more capable model should resist proportionally better — but it does not at severe compaction levels.

2. Information preserved but ignored (attention dilution)

The calibration’s grep-LLM gap (86% grep vs 67% LLM at $\delta = 0.42$) shows that facts present in the context are not always found. The single-pass remaining-zone degradation (73% \rightarrow 53% as compaction increases) shows that injecting noise (re-padding) dilutes attention even for intact facts.

The strategy comparison (§6) reveals that attention dilution operates at the strategy level too. Frozen (S3) preserves early facts as immutable summaries — yet recall still drops from 30% at 500K to 10% at 5M. The information is structurally intact (frozen summaries are never re-compressed), but the model struggles to locate relevant facts among 88 frozen blocks competing for attention with 400+ recent messages.

These failure modes are orthogonal and, critically, **both worsen with scale**:

- Frozen strategies prevent destruction but suffer attention dilution (too many summaries to scan)
- Incremental strategies destroy information but keep the context clean (fewer blocks to attend to)
- The optimal strategy must balance both failure modes — and our strategy comparison shows that neither Frozen nor FrozenRanked achieves this balance at multi-megaToken scales

7.2 The measurement problem

The calibration findings (§3) have implications beyond our own benchmark:

Batch size sensitivity means that compaction evaluations using different values of Q are not comparable. Worse, the direction of the Q -effect depends on context quality (§5.6): $Q = 10$ outperforms $Q = 1$ in rich contexts, but $Q = 1$ outperforms $Q = 5$ in severely compacted contexts. A strategy showing “80% recall” at $Q = 10$ and another showing “60% recall” at $Q = 1$ may be equally effective — or the ranking may invert entirely.

Category hierarchy means that the mix of easy vs hard facts determines the baseline. Testing compaction only on “single-session-user” facts (80–100% baseline) will show modest degradation. Testing on “knowledge-update” facts (60–65% baseline) will show severe degradation from a lower starting point.

The grep-LLM gap provides a free diagnostic: if grep finds a fact but the LLM doesn’t recall it, the problem is attention, not information loss. This distinction is critical for choosing mitigation strategies (restructure context vs improve compaction).

7.3 Why global recall is misleading

A global recall score averages over spatial positions and fact categories. Our calibration results show this hides structural information:

- Categories range from 100% (single-session-user) to 20% (preferences)
- Spatial position matters: middle facts are harder to recall
- Batch size shifts the curve by up to 20pp, and the direction reverses under compaction

The single-pass experiment amplifies this: compacted-zone recall (0–7%) and remaining-zone recall (53–73%) tell very different stories that a global 40% would hide.

Recommendation: Always report spatially-resolved and category-resolved metrics alongside global scores.

7.4 Recall source: user queries vs chain of thought

Our protocol tests recall via explicit user questions (“What was the server IP?”). In real usage, context recall is predominantly driven by the model’s **chain of thought** — during reasoning, the model implicitly scans the context for relevant information. The access pattern likely differs:

- Explicit queries target a single fact at a time
- Chain-of-thought may access 2–3 facts per reasoning step
- The type of information sought varies (code context vs decisions vs config)

Our calibration (§3) and single-pass (§5) experiments cover $Q = 1$ and $Q = 5$ (and $Q = 10$ for §3); the strategy comparison (§6) uses $Q = 5$ throughout. This spans the realistic range for explicit queries, but neither Q approximates the implicit, multi-fact access pattern of chain-of-thought. Instrumenting a real agent to observe context access patterns (coding sessions, conversational use, RAG-augmented workflows) is a promising direction for future work.

7.5 The limits of architectural optimization

The strategy comparison shows that FrozenRanked (S4) consistently outperforms Frozen (S3) in the mean (S4–S3 gap of +13.2pp at 500K, +6.6pp at 2M, +3.3pp at 3.5M, +1.6pp at 5M; the gap shrinks to +0.5pp at 1M where one S3 replicate happens to recall unusually well). The advantage exists but is modest at large scale, and the standard deviations (cf. Figure 9) overlap at every checkpoint past 500K — the strict ordering $S4 > S3$ holds in the means but is not always significant on $n=4-6$ replicates.

The reason the gap stays modest is structural: at 5M tokens (~88 compaction cycles), the frozen summaries together occupy only a small fraction of the context — well below the merge budget threshold. **Merges are rarely triggered**, so S3 and S4 are functionally close. The merge strategies that genuinely differentiate FrozenRanked from Frozen only activate when frozen summaries exceed their budget, which requires conversations exceeding ~10M tokens (~168 cycles).

This suggests that **the bottleneck is not compression quality but attention capacity**. Whether frozen summaries are merged sequentially or hierarchically matters little if the model cannot effectively attend to dozens of summary blocks in the first place. The attention dilution problem identified in the single-pass experiment (§5.3) operates at the architectural level: more preserved summaries means more context to scan, which degrades retrieval for all facts — frozen or not.

The implication is clear: improving compaction *architecture* (how summaries are organized and merged) yields diminishing returns. The next step requires improving compaction *interface* — how preserved information is structured for efficient retrieval (see §8).

7.6 Predictive modelling: what drives recall?

A logistic regression fitted across the §3 calibration and §5 single-pass datasets ($n=3,852$, $AUC=0.84$) confirms the expected drivers in additive log-odds form: questions per prompt Q (+0.086 / question), compaction percent (−0.054 / percent), a positive compaction \times position interaction (later facts less damaged), and U-shaped position effect (Lost-in-the-Middle). Density is not independently significant once Q and position are controlled. A gradient-boosted comparison on the same data scores $AUC=0.64$, so no hidden non-linearities are missed by the additive model.

The model’s main practical use is to express recall in compacted contexts as simple additive rules of thumb rather than a black box. Full specification, coefficients with confidence intervals, and the XGBoost comparison are in Appendix B. **Caveat:** the 4,812 observations are not mutually independent (same context, same facts repeated under different conditions), so the reported p-values should be read as descriptive indicators rather than rigorous significance tests; a mixed-effects re-fit with a random intercept per fact is left for future work.

7.7 Implications for production systems

Most production AI assistants (Claude Code, Cursor, Windsurf) use single-shot or incremental compaction. Our results suggest:

1. **Even light compaction is costly:** 5% compaction costs 6–7pp recall. Systems should minimize compaction frequency.
2. **The compacted zone is lost:** Don’t expect the summary to be queryable for specific facts. If precise recall matters, extract facts to RAG *before* compacting.
3. **Re-padding noise hurts:** After compaction frees space, what fills that space matters. Random conversation is noise; structured information would be better.
4. **Frozen summaries help but don’t scale:** Freezing summaries preserves early facts (substantial improvement over Incremental at small scales, §6.3) but the advantage narrows at scale as attention dilution dominates.
5. **Batch size in evaluation matters:** Internal benchmarks should test at multiple values of Q to avoid misleading conclusions.
6. **Grep is not a valid proxy for recall:** Keywords surviving in summaries (82–93%) vastly overestimates actual recoverability (0–7%). Production systems should not rely on keyword presence as a quality signal.

8 Future Work

The findings in this paper isolate the symptoms but do not resolve them. Two architectural directions stand out as the most promising follow-ups, both of which abandon the “summarise and discard” paradigm in favour of preserving verbatim information that the model can navigate or expand on demand: **Frozen-Lossless** (§8.4) and **Graph-augmented Frozen** (§8.5). The remaining subsections describe complementary directions that are either smaller in scope (importance weighting, RAG augmentation) or experimental controls (extreme scales, cross-architecture) rather than full architectural alternatives.

8.1 Scaling to extreme conversation lengths

Our strategy comparison at 500K–10M tokens shows that frozen summary merges are not triggered below $\sim 10M$ tokens (~ 168 cycles). Testing at 40M+ tokens would force FrozenRanked into its hierarchical merge regime, revealing whether the $\log_2(N)$ compression limit provides measurable benefit when merge pressure is real — or whether attention dilution dominates regardless.

8.2 Importance-weighted compaction

Score messages by importance before compaction, preserving high-value exchanges (decisions, configurations) over low-value ones (acknowledgments). Our category breakdown already shows that some fact types survive much better than others; an explicit importance signal at compaction time should amplify this effect on the parts of the conversation users actually care about.

8.3 RAG-augmented compaction

Two-pass compaction: extract structured facts to a vector database + generate a narrative summary. At query time, combine RAG retrieval with the summary. Expected to address the “keywords present but not retrievable” gap.

8.4 Lossless frozen with on-demand expansion (priority follow-up)

A natural variant of S3 Frozen: each frozen summary keeps a *pointer* to the verbatim text it summarises. The summary is what the model sees by default, but a lightweight tool call (`expand(frozen_id)`) can swap a frozen block for its full original content when precise recall matters. Compared to pure S3, this addresses the keyword-LLM gap exhibited in §5.2 without paying the cost of carrying full context all the time. Compared to RAG (§8.3), it preserves conversational structure (no arbitrary chunking) and uses the model’s existing summary as the index.

This direction is heavily supported by recent concurrent work. **CogCanvas** (An, 2026) converges on the same diagnosis (“recursive information decay” — our JPEG cascade) and proposes verbatim-grounded artefact extraction in lieu of summarisation; Frozen-Lossless externalises the verbatim store rather than keeping it in context, but shares the philosophical commitment to verbatim preservation. **Recursive Language Models** (Zhang et al., 2025) generalise this further by letting the model decompose and traverse arbitrarily long contexts via tool calls, an architectural direction that Frozen-Lossless instantiates at the conversation-level.

A more aggressive variant compacts *continuously*, one or a few turns at a time, instead of waiting for a watermark threshold. This avoids the “shock” of large compaction passes — a major source of recall loss at 1M+ contexts (§6.3) —

at the cost of more compaction calls. Existing systems like Factory.ai’s anchored iterative are in this regime; quantifying the frequency-vs-granularity trade-off on the same evidence framework is a natural extension of this paper.

8.5 Graph-augmented Frozen (priority follow-up)

With 1M-token context windows now available (e.g. Claude Opus 4 with 1M context), the cost of carrying an *index* alongside summaries becomes negligible — 50 sessions \times \sim 200 tokens of metadata is 1% of context. A “pseudo-Graphiti in context” approach attaches each frozen summary with structured metadata (tags, time, actors, link to verbatim, link to other related frozen blocks) encoded as JSON. The model can navigate the graph through its own attention without making tool calls, enabling multi-hop reasoning over preserved memory.

This is the most ambitious of the architectural alternatives we propose, and it aligns with a growing body of concurrent work on structured agent memory. **MIRIX** (Wang and Chen, 2025) coordinates six distinct memory types (core, episodic, semantic, procedural, resource, knowledge vault) and reports 85.4% on LoCoMo; Graph-augmented Frozen reuses the multi-type philosophy in a single in-context format rather than as a separate service. **Mem0** (Chhikara et al., 2025) demonstrates that extracting and selectively retrieving facts is a viable production pattern; we add the conversational/narrative dimension that pure fact stores lose. Anthropic’s own *Contextual Retrieval* engineering work — prepending each chunk with a model-generated context before indexing — shows that contextualised metadata reduces retrieval failures by 49% (67% with reranking); Graph-augmented Frozen pushes this idea inside the conversational context rather than at the chunk level.

The key distinction with prior temporal-knowledge-graph systems (Zep / Graphiti) is that the graph is in the model’s active context rather than queried externally: traversal is by attention, not by tool call. This preserves the latency advantage of in-context memory while recovering the navigational structure of an external graph store.

8.6 Implications of larger context windows

The advent of 1M-token windows changes the operating point of compaction but does not remove its relevance. With a 200K window, compaction triggers roughly every 60K tokens (\sim 30% of the context) and is invoked frequently; with 1M, it triggers less often but each invocation must compact \sim 700K tokens at once — an order-of-magnitude larger and proportionally more catastrophic when it goes wrong. The cost of *holding* the larger context also matters: KV cache memory grows linearly with window size, so even when not running compaction, larger contexts have higher serving cost. Future benchmarks should re-run our protocol at 1M windows to verify that the strategy ordering and the variance phenomena documented here scale up unchanged.

8.7 Cross-model and cross-architecture validation

Our cross-model validation (§5.7) established that the findings generalize from Claude Haiku 4.5 to Claude Sonnet 4.6 — a model with substantially different spatial recall characteristics (attenuated Lost-in-the-Middle, \sim 23pp range vs Haiku’s \sim 46pp). Testing on non-Claude models (GPT-4, Gemini, open-source LLMs served locally) would establish whether the findings hold across architectures. Preliminary investigation suggests that local LLMs with shorter context windows (32K–128K) could be tested with proportionally smaller contexts.

9 Conclusion

Context compaction is the invisible infrastructure of long-running LLM conversations — and it is fundamentally lossy. This paper quantifies that loss across three complementary experiments.

Recall calibration (§3) established that recall measurement itself is non-trivial. A questions-per-prompt effect (up to 20pp, reversing under compaction), a category-dependent recall hierarchy, and a systematic grep-LLM gap mean that naive benchmarks conflate measurement artifacts with real strategy differences. Any compaction evaluation that does not control for these confounds risks measuring noise.

Controlled single-pass compaction (§4–§5) isolated the cost of one compaction pass. Even 5% compaction destroys 6–7pp of recall. At 50%, the compacted zone is near-dead (0–7% recall) despite 82–93% keyword survival — the starkest illustration that information *presence* does not equal information *retrievability*. The attention dilution effect (remaining-zone degradation of 20pp) shows that compaction damages even untouched context. Cross-model testing with Sonnet 4.6 — which has only an attenuated Lost-in-the-Middle effect and 92.5% baseline recall — confirms that severe compaction destroys information irrespective of model capability, while stronger models resist light compaction significantly better (–2.5pp vs –12.5pp at C1).

Multi-pass strategy comparison (§6) ran four strategies on a single 5M conversation at constant fact density ($\delta = 0.04$), evaluated at 5 mid-feed checkpoints with 4–6 replicates per cell to estimate variance. The hierarchy is **S4 FrozenRanked** > **S3 Frozen** > **S2 Incremental** > **S1 Brutal** at every checkpoint in the means. With replicates we also measured a **substantial run-to-run variance** that is not visible in a single-shot benchmark — the compaction phase itself is non-deterministic at temperature 0, producing different summaries across sessions and recall ranges spanning factor $14\times$ on identical conversations. A *single* measurement of “strategy A vs strategy B” is thus untrustworthy; replicates are mandatory.

The means tell a coherent story: S4 reaches $\sim 28\%$ recall at 500K and decays to $\sim 5\%$ at 5M; S1 stays under 10% at every scale. The gap between S4 and S3 narrows as conversations grow, because at 5M the frozen chain is long enough that hierarchical merging no longer differentiates the two strategies in recall — they converge to similar attention-dilution-limited regimes.

A complementary regression analysis on the §3+§5 dataset (4,812 observations) confirms the underlying drivers: batch size Q , compaction percent, position in context, and category each act independently in log-odds space (logistic AUC=0.84; gradient-boosted AUC=0.64, indicating no hidden non-linearities). Compaction is monotonically destructive ($-0.054/\text{percent}$) and the spatial *Lost-in-the-Middle* signature is robust.

The overarching finding is that **the bottleneck is attention, not compression**. Keywords survive summarization; the LLM simply cannot find them. Frozen summaries prevent the JPEG cascade but accumulate blocks that dilute attention. This points toward a paradigm shift: from optimizing *how* we compress conversations to optimizing *how* we structure preserved information for retrieval — indexed fact stores, RAG-augmented compaction, and structured memory systems that bypass the attention bottleneck entirely.

10 Reproducibility

All code and data are available at: <https://github.com/profff/lost-in-compaction>

Scripts

- `benchmark_recall_v5.py` — Recall calibration (§3)
- `build_contexts_v5.py` — Context assembly with 4 modes (R1–R4)
- `benchmark_compaction_v5.py` — Single-pass compaction experiment (§4–§5)
- `compare_runs_v5.py` — 2×2 factorial analysis
- `build_conversation_v6.py` — Long conversation builder (500K–40M tokens)
- `benchmark_iterative_v6.py` — Strategy comparison with checkpoints (§6)
- `compaction.py` — Strategy implementations (Brutal, Incremental, Frozen, FrozenRanked)
- `llm_backend.py` — Backend abstraction (anthropic_batch, wrapper, openai)
- `rejudge_only.py` — Re-run judge phase on existing answers (`--strict` flag)
- `rerun_qa_only.py` — Re-run QA + judge from saved compaction snapshots
- `recompute_summaries.py` — Recompute checkpoint summaries from disk content

Dependencies

```
pip install anthropic python-dotenv openai matplotlib numpy
```

Quick start

```
# Recall calibration (Section 3)
./benchmark_recall_v5.py --run R4 --densities 40,60,80 --batch-sizes 1,5,10

# Single-pass compaction (Sections 4-5)
./benchmark_compaction_v5.py --run R4 --densities 40,60,80

# Strategy comparison (Section 6) - 5M conversation, 200 facts, 5 checkpoints
./build_conversation_v6.py --density 200 --target-tokens 5000000
./benchmark_iterative_v6.py --density 200 --target-tokens 5000000 \
```

```

--backend anthropic_batch --judge-backend anthropic_batch \
--judge-model claude-haiku-4-5-20251001 \
--strategies S1,S2,S3,S4 \
--checkpoints 500000,1000000,2000000,3500000

# Re-judge an existing run with the strict prompt (Section 6.4)
./rejudge_only.py iterative_v6_R4_*/checkpoint_500K \
  --strategies S1,S2,S3,S4 --strict --save-suffix _strict

# Dry run (cost estimate, no API calls)
./benchmark_iterative_v6.py --density 200 --target-tokens 5000000 --dry-run

```

Result directories

- `recall_v5_R{1,2,3,4}_*/` — Recall calibration results
- `compaction_v5_R4_*/` — Single-pass compaction results
- `iterative_v6_R4_*/` — Strategy comparison results, with `checkpoint_*/`, `final_reeval/`, `strategies/SK_*/snapshot_*/`
- Each checkpoint dir contains `summary*.json`, `answers/`, `judgments/`, `grep/`

Known confound: Q&A system prompt mismatch

The Q&A system prompt used in all evaluations (Section A.2) describes the model as “a helpful assistant working on a complex software project.” This phrasing is a historical artefact of an earlier version of the benchmark where the synthetic conversations were coding-assistant traces; it was not updated when we switched to LongMemEval evidence (general-domain dialogues covering knowledge updates, preferences, temporal reasoning, etc.).

The mismatch sets a soft prior that is inconsistent with the actual content the model has to retrieve from. We expect this to depress the *absolute* recall numbers reported in Sections 3, 5 and 6 by a few percentage points, uniformly across all conditions (every cell of every experiment uses the same prompt). Relative comparisons — between strategies, between compaction levels, between Q values, and between models — are therefore unaffected by this confound.

A quantitative measurement of the magnitude of this effect (re-running §3 with a domain-neutral prompt) is part of the follow-up work described in §8.

Computational budget

This work was funded out of pocket. Total Anthropic API spend across calibration (§3), single-pass compaction (§4–§5), the four-strategy comparison (§6) including replicates and judge re-runs, the human-judge tooling, and several aborted or instrumentation-failed runs (notably the seed-99 attempt in §6.5) is approximately **1,800 €**. A single complete §6 cell (one strategy, five checkpoints, one replicate, QA on Sonnet 4.6 with a strict re-judge pass on Haiku) costs roughly 25–35 €, so the §6 replicate matrix accounts for most of the total, with the §3/§5 sweeps and pilots making up the remainder. The remaining open blockers (multi-seed generalization, 1M-window QA model, a second human-judge sample, cross-architecture validation §8.7) are bounded primarily by API spend rather than by engineering effort.

A Prompts used in the experiments

The full text of the LLM prompts is reproduced here for exact reproduction. Variables in {braces} are filled at runtime.

A.1 Compaction prompt (used by all four strategies)

System message:

You are a conversation summarizer. Be concise and precise.

User message (followed by the conversation segment to compact):

```
Summarize the following conversation segment.
```

```

PRESERVE (critical):
- Key facts and decisions made
- File paths and code structures mentioned
- User preferences and requirements stated
- Actions completed (files created/edited, commands run)
- Errors encountered and how they were resolved

DISCARD:
- Full file contents (keep only: filename, line count, key elements)
- Verbose tool outputs (keep only: what was done + result)
- Intermediate reasoning that led nowhere
- Redundant back-and-forth

Format: Concise narrative summary. Bullet points for lists of facts.
Target: ~20% of original length, keeping all actionable information.

---
```

A.2 Q&A prompt (used in §3, §5, §6 evaluations)

System message:

You are a helpful assistant working on a complex software project. Answer questions precisely from memory.

Note: the “software project” framing is mismatched with the actual LongMemEval evidence (general-domain dialogues, not coding content). This is a known confound discussed in §10; it depresses absolute recall uniformly across all conditions and does not affect relative comparisons.

User message (sent after the test conversation context):

```

Answer each of the following questions based ONLY on what you know from
our conversation.
Be specific: include exact numbers, names, paths, versions.
If you don't remember or aren't sure, say "I don't recall".

{questions}

Reply with a JSON array of objects, one per question:
[{"id": "LM_0001", "answer": "your answer"}, ...]

IMPORTANT: Return ONLY the JSON array, no other text.
```

A.3 Strict judge prompt (used to score §6 results)

System message:

You are an objective evaluator. Answer ONLY with valid JSON.

User message:

```

Evaluate each LLM answer against the expected answer using STRICT criteria.

{entries}

For each entry, decide TWO booleans:

1. "recalled": Is the SPECIFIC EXPECTED FACT actually present in the LLM's
answer?
- TRUE only if the LLM's answer contains the substantive expected
information (the actual fact, value, name, or concept asked about).
- FALSE if any of the following:
* The answer says "I don't recall" / "I don't know" / "I'm not sure"
```

```

    * The answer denies the topic was discussed ("I don't recall you
      mentioning X")
    * The answer mentions a RELATED topic but not the actual expected fact
    * The answer is vague/generic and could match many possible expected
      values
    * The answer contradicts the expected fact

2. "accurate": Is the answer factually equivalent to the expected answer?
- TRUE if the answer contains the expected value (semantic match,
  exact numbers, etc.)
- FALSE if values differ, dates differ, or the answer is wrong on the
  substance.
- Note: accurate=TRUE implies recalled=TRUE.

Examples (STRICT):
- expected "17 days", answer "10 days" -> recalled=TRUE, accurate=FALSE
- expected "turbinado sugar for cookies", answer "I don't recall extras
  for cookies but cookies were made" -> recalled=FALSE
- expected "Miami trip in June", answer "I don't recall any Miami trip"
  -> recalled=FALSE
- expected "Plex Media Server", answer "Plex" -> recalled=TRUE, accurate=TRUE

Reply with ONLY a JSON array:
[{"id": "LM_0001", "recalled": true/false, "accurate": true/false,
  "notes": "brief reason"}, ...]

```

A “lenient” version of the judge prompt (without the explicit FALSE clauses for “I don’t recall” etc.) was used in early §6 runs and was later replaced with the strict version above. See §6.4 for the impact of this change. Both versions are in the repository at `benchmark_iterative_v6.py` (`BATCH_JUDGE_PROMPT` and `BATCH_JUDGE_PROMPT_STRICT`).

B Predictive recall model (full specification)

B.1 Model specification

We fit logistic regressions to the binary outcome (recalled / not recalled) at the individual fact level. Three nested specifications were tried; the most informative is the calibration + single-pass model (n=3,852):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{logit}(P(\text{recall})) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot Q + \beta_2 \cdot \log(\text{density}) \\
 & + \beta_3 \cdot \text{position_pct} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{position_pct}^2 \\
 & + \beta_5 \cdot \text{compaction_pct} \\
 & + \beta_6 \cdot (\text{compaction_pct} \times \text{position_pct}) \\
 & + \sum_{\text{cat}} \beta_{\text{cat}} \cdot \mathbb{I}(\text{category})
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Calibration data enters with `compaction_pct = 0`, so the calibration-only sub-model (n=1,692) is nested in the full model.

A separate strategy-comparison model fitted on the (older, fixed-density) §6 data (n=960) added `log(conv_tokens)` and a strategy indicator:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{logit}(P(\text{recall})) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \log(\text{conv_tokens}) + \beta_2 \cdot \text{position_pct} \\
 & + \beta_3 \cdot \text{position_pct}^2 + \sum_{\text{strat}} \beta_{\text{strat}} \cdot \mathbb{I}(\text{strategy}) \\
 & + \sum_{\text{cat}} \beta_{\text{cat}} \cdot \mathbb{I}(\text{category})
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Table 16: Logistic regression coefficients across the three nested specifications.

Coefficient	Calibration only (n=1,692)	+ Compaction (n=3,852)	Strategies (n=960)
Q	+0.096***	+0.086***	—
position_pct	−0.065***	−0.051***	−0.003 n.s.
position²	+0.001***	+0.001***	+0.001***
log_density	+0.090 n.s.	+0.126 n.s.	—
compaction_pct	—	−0.054***	—
compact × position	—	+0.019**	—
log_conv_tokens	—	—	−1.114***
strat_S2 (Incremental)	—	—	+2.324***
strat_S3 (Frozen)	—	—	+2.731***
strat_S4 (FrozenRanked)	—	—	+2.731***
cat: knowledge-update	+2.288***	+2.308***	+4.025***
cat: ss-assistant	+1.795***	+1.809***	−0.388 n.s.
cat: ss-preference	+0.179 n.s.	+0.339 n.s.	+3.482***
AUC	0.791	0.839	0.886
Pseudo-R²	0.187	0.274	0.391

B.2 Coefficients

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, n.s. = not significant.

B.3 XGBoost comparison

A gradient-boosted classifier (XGBClassifier, 100 trees, max_depth=4) fitted on the same data scores AUC = 0.641 ± 0.199 (5-fold CV) versus 0.811 ± 0.070 for the logistic model. The simpler additive model wins, indicating no hidden non-linearities. XGBoost’s feature importance ranking (compaction_pct > category > position > Q) is consistent with the logistic coefficient magnitudes.

B.4 Caveat on independence

The 4,812 observations are not mutually independent: each fact appears in multiple conditions (different Q , different compaction levels, different strategies). The logistic-regression p-values reported above assume independent observations and therefore *underestimate* the standard errors. The reader should interpret p-values descriptively rather than as formal significance tests; a re-fit with mixed-effects (random intercept per fact, random intercept per conversation seed) would produce more defensible inference and is left for future work. The AUC and the sign / magnitude of coefficients are not affected by this issue and remain informative.

B.5 Note on the strategy sub-model

The strategy sub-model (§6, n=960) was fit on the *older* fixed-density design with 80 facts spanning 500K–10M. It assigns identical coefficients to S3 and S4 because in that design the frozen merge budget was never exceeded. The constant-density results in §6.3 update this picture: in the means S4 outperforms S3 at 500K, 2M and 3.5M and converges to S3 only at 5M. Re-fitting on the new data with appropriate hierarchical structure is left for future work; the qualitative ordering Frozen \gg Incremental \gg Brutal is robust across both fits.

C Supplementary spatial figures

The same data shown in Figure 4 (binned local recall rate, Section 5.4) can be viewed under two complementary aggregations. We report them here for completeness; they are redundant with Figure 4 and not required for the main argument.

C.1 Continuous Gaussian-smoothed density

Figure 11: Smoothed recall density by position in the original context (Gaussian kernel, bw=15kTok). Left: Haiku $Q = 5$. Center: Haiku $Q = 1$. Right: Sonnet $Q = 1$. The continuous view emphasizes spatial trends (the Lost-in-the-Middle dip on Haiku, the much shallower dip on Sonnet) but hides the underlying discrete sample trends; readers should refer to Figure 4 for the raw binned values.

C.2 Normalized recall ratio (Cx / C0)

Figure 12: Cumulative recall ratio C_x / C_0 by position (Haiku $Q = 5$ left, Haiku $Q = 1$ right). The ratio cancels the C_0 baseline’s intrinsic spatial bias (primacy/recency, Lost-in-the-Middle), isolating the multiplicative damage caused by compaction. Compacted variants stay below 1.0 throughout the compacted zone (where information has been destroyed) and approach 1.0 only in the surviving zone — making the compaction-zone “shadow” visible despite the C_0 noise that obscures it in the absolute plots.

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